

DICAM

DIPARTIMENTO DI INGEGNERIA CIVILE, CHIMICA, AMBIENTALE E DEI MATERIALI

OPEN_MASK_LAB

A virtual open lab for sharing mask tests design, analysis and calibration

TECHNICAL REPORT V2

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Introduction

During the COVID-19 emergency, Europe has faced a shortage of medical and protective masks, as many European Countries had abandoned the production of such goods and their exportation was severely limited by the National Governments.

At the same time, many companies that decided to start producing masks for the emergency in support of the medical staff were slowed down by the scarcity of authorized certification labs that could test their products under the current EU standards.

For this reason, a multidisciplinary team based at the University of Bologna spontaneously formed including researchers of the Biology, Occupational Health and Chemical Engineering areas. The group managed to build and set-up within a week, with the help of donations from private and public

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entities, the equipment for tests according to standard EN 14683 (breathability, bacterial filtration, splash). Part of this facilities are based at the MEMLAB in the Civil, Chemical, Environmental and Materials Engineering Department, and others in a sterile room at the University Hospital “Sant’Orsola” in Bologna.

The lesson learned from this story is that Europe needs to become fully independent in the production and testing of protective masks in order to be ready to tackle the current and future pandemics, and one of the ways to achieve that goal, that is the aim of the present project, is by making the knowledge about how to build and carry out testing equipment fully available for free to a wider public.

For this reason, the project OPEN_MASK_LAB aims at sharing the knowledge gained by the group about sampling test methodologies for protective masks through the set-up of a virtual open lab. Such activity has been carried out by building a [website](#) where documents, data, reports, papers, video tutorials, pictures, charts and schemes are collected. Other groups can use the website to share their data and information.

The budget of the project has been used for building the website, as well as to purchase new pieces of equipment required for tests.

Methodology

A medical face mask is a device covering the mouth, nose and chin ensuring a barrier that limits the transition of an infective agent between the hospital staff and the patient. They are used by healthcare workers to prevent large respiratory droplets and splashes from reaching the mouth and the nose of the wearer and help reduce and/or control at the source the spread of large respiratory droplets from the person wearing the mask. A medical face mask needs to obey an official standard description (EN 14683:2019 in Europe or ASTM F2100-19 in the US), but during the COVID-19 outbreak the Italian National Institute of Health (ISS) has allowed, limited to the emergency period, the use of surgical masks without the CE mark after evaluation by the ISS. The procedure requires the execution of different tests following International Standard procedures, and in particular following the EN 14683:2019 standard that is the current European norm, the ASTM F2100-19 in the US standard. Masks defined under the EN 14683:2019 standard are classified into two types according to their bacterial filtration efficiency (BFE) level and their comfort in breathability. Type I masks have a $BFE \geq 95\%$ and a $\Delta P < 40 \text{ Pa/cm}^2$; type II and IIR masks have a $BFE \geq 98\%$ and a $\Delta P < 40$ or 60 Pa/cm^2 for type II and IIR, respectively. The latter needs also to pass the splash test, which is related to the resistance to the penetration of a splash of synthetic blood with a pressure $> 16 \text{ kPa}$. Masks that meet the level 1 and level 2 requirements of the ASTM F2100-19 standard are equivalent to type I and type II masks, respectively, of the EN 14683:2019 standard. Additionally, performance requirements of medical face masks include a microbial cleanliness (i.e., the bioburden of the mask) < 30 colony-forming units (CFUs)/g. Medical face masks should be also tested for their biocompatibility according to ISO 10993-5 and 10, which specifies cytotoxicity and skin sensitivity test methods to ensure the materials are not harmful to the wearer.

A brief description of the tests is reported hereafter.

BREATHABILITY

Such test is of paramount importance for a surgical mask because, unlike respirators (personal protective equipment, PPE), there are no specific element that provide a good adhesion with the face, and thus the sealing of the equipment is poor. Hence, if the resistance to the air flow caused by the masks is too high, a fraction of the air passes through the boundaries instead that through the mask, reducing the protection offered by the device.

The Differential Pressure or Breathability test is the direct measure of the respiratory resistance provided by the mask, evaluated as pressure drop at fixed flow, and it is thus correlated to the effort required by the wearer in order to breath with conventional inhalation/exhalation rates. Taking

advantage of the uniformity of the surgical mask, the tests are executed on a representative section, a circular sample of 25 mm of diameter (i.e. 4.91 cm² of area), in which the pressure drop need to be measured when impacted by 8 L/min air flow;

Such test is of paramount importance not only for the respiratory effort for the wearer, but also because, unlike respirators (personal protective equipment, PPE), surgical masks do not contain specific element that provide a good adhesion with the face, and thus the sealing of the equipment is poor. Hence, if the resistance to the air flow caused by the masks is too high, a fraction of the air passes through the boundaries instead that through the mask, reducing the protection offered by the device.

Figure 1: Breathability test apparatus

Figure 1 reports the layout of the test rig set-up in our laboratory in which one can distinguish the sample holder, a U-tube manometer (maximum reading 2 kPa, accuracy 1 Pa), a flow meter (range 0-500 L/h) and a regulation valve.

In the apparatus set-up during the emergency time, two different configurations have been prepared, one according to the standard norm, in which the air flow (and thus the pressure difference) is generated by a vacuum pump that pulls air from the section downstream to the mask sample, with upstream section connected to the atmosphere. A second configuration considers the upstream compartment in slight overpressure with compressed air and with the downstream sections at atmospheric pressure. Relevantly, no differences have been observed in the resulting Δp measured at the inspected flow rates, so the latter one has been considered in the light of a slightly easier set-up and the absence of region in the test rig with pressure under vacuum, thus ruling out any possible infiltration from the external air.

In brief, the compressed air is fed to the apparatus and its flow rate is controlled by a dedicated valve and by means of an analogic flowmeter. The sample holder is composed by two stainless steel T-pipes, having an internal diameter of 25 mm and tri-clamp connections at all the extremities, used, as represented in the figure for the connections with the differential manometer.

The samples are prepared by punching with a hollow cutter (25 mm diameter) the prototype mask in different positions. Then, after appropriate conditioning for at least 4 h at 85% R.H. at room temperature (obtained by potassium chloride KCl supersaturated solutions [[i],[ii]] in a closed box), the samples are placed between the clamp connections of the two tubes and sealed with flat, rubber

ring gaskets with an internal diameter of 25 mm, placed above and below the specimen to ensure tightness and the correct sample cross-sectional area.

Figure 2: example of the experimental output from a breathability test

The experimental procedure developed in order to minimize the experimental error and to ensure the repeatability of the test considers the measure of the pressure drop at multiple flow rates, namely 100, 200, 300, 400, 450, 500 L/h at least twice per each specimen. A linear correlation is typically detected, and the slope allowed the determination of the pressure difference at 8 L/min (480 L/h). An example of the data output is reported in a chart in Figure 2. The final value reported for each specimen is the arithmetic mean of the different measurements (at list two), after its division by sample area, as indicated in the norm.

[i] Standard Practice for Maintaining Constant Relative Humidity by Means of Aqueous Solutions, ASTM E104 – 02 (2012), ASTM International, West Conshohocken, PA 19428-2959. United States.

[ii] L. Greenspan, Humidity Fixed Points of Binary Saturated Aqueous Solutions, J. Res. Nat. Bureau Stand. A Phys. Chem. 81 (1977) 89-96.

BACTERIAL FILTRATION EFFICIENCY (BFE)

The design of the BFE apparatus requires several specific instruments, as indicated in the layout of the system developed according to the standard norm indications. Due to the full lockdown in the pandemic outbreak in spring 2020 and the short time available required by the urgent needs, not all such pieces of equipment were on the market. Therefore, we were forced to adapt components already presents in our laboratories, spare parts, and even pieces disassembled from other apparatuses. Other components were generously donated by companies, citizens or other University of Bologna Departments. Over the subsequent months and for the whole 2020, the initial version of the apparatus has been improved.

The first version of the BFE apparatus, illustrated in the Figure was installed in a disused **surgery room** at the University hospital (St. Orsola), in order to exploit of the sterile conditions required for the tests and for a higher safety of the workers.

The air, coming from the sterile room, enters in a transparent, poly methyl methacrylate (PMMA) **tube**, with an internal diameter of 80 mm and flanged at both ends. [See Figure 4 note 1]

At half of the tube height (700 mm), a pressure driven **nebulizer** (Collison single-jet nebulizer by CHT technologies) nebulizes a ***Staphylococcus aureus* solution**.

The two-phase mixture produced in the cylinder reaches the bottom where the **mask sample**, appropriately cut of the size requested by the standard norm, is placed between two flanges.

The bottom flange was connected to the underneath impactor by a **connection** specifically designed by the software Autodesk Inventor 2019 and produced by a **3D printer** (Prusa i3 MK3S+).

The bacteria containing droplets permeating through the mask sample are collected in an **Andersen 6-stages impactor**, generously donated by **Cavazza Anna SAS (Bologna, Italy)**. The impactor is able to collect droplets of different sizes, with diameter down to 0.65 μm .

To avoid any possible diffusion of bacteria in the environment, smaller contaminated droplets are collected in a **vacuum trap**, preceded by a glass, water cooled condenser. To this aim, two different configurations have been considered, the first one, using tap water available in the operating theatre, while later, a mini-chiller has been implemented in the system, in order to reduce the water consumption a to ensure proper cooling also during warmest periods.

The droplet-free air finally reaches a **flow indicator** (Bronkhorst el-flow, range 0-100 L/min) generously donated by **IMA SpA (Ozzano Emilia (Bologna), Italy)**, a valve for flow regulation and a vacuum pump that provides the required driving force for the air flow. [2]

The **aerosol** used during the tests consists of a bacterial suspension of *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC6538, which is prepared at a concentration of $5 \cdot 10^5$ CFU colony forming units (CFU) /mL by diluting 1/7000 a culture with 1.8 McFarland turbidity standard in modified peptone water (peptone 5 g/L, NaCl 5 g/L). This inoculum preparation allows to test approximately $1.7 - 3 \times 10^3$ CFU per test (as suggested by the standard norm).

The bacterial aerosol is transported inside the tube thanks to the activity of a **vacuum pump** placed at the end of the test line with a flow rate of **28.3 L/min**. This will force the aerosol to pass through the mask, and the bacteria not retained by the mask are collected in the stages of the **impactor**, where 6 horse blood agar **petri dishes** are placed, one for each impactor stage.

The **bacterial colonies** (CFU) that will grow on these plates are counted after a 24-48 h incubation at 37 °C.

The number of CFU grown on the plates are used to calculate the BFE by comparing the total CFU obtained by testing 5 masks with the number of CFU present in the bacterial aerosol (see e.g., Figure 2d).

The mean value and the standard deviation have been calculated using the CFU data from the 5 different specimens obtained by 5 different masks analyzed. To assess the absence of environmental contamination, a negative control was also performed, by letting air flow through the impactor, in the absence of both the mask and the nebulized bacterial aerosol starting from the suspension of the inoculum.

Notes

[1] Pipe length and material: The normative requires a glass tube with an internal diameter of 80 mm and a height of 600 mm, from the top of which the aerosol enters. No interferences between the plastic tube and the aerosol bacteria were observed, as shown by all the negative control run performed during the entire period of investigation that demonstrated the absence of contamination in the tube. However, after the emergency time and by the end of the lockdown period, the plastic PMMA tube was replaced by the standard glassy tube, prepared strictly according to the standard norm and no differences were observed in the results obtained.

[2] Air flow humidity: Interestingly, the standard norm contains specific indications about the conditioning protocol for the specimens (room T at 85% R.H. for at least 4 h), while there is no mention about the humidity of the feed air used for the test, even though that is very relevant in the case of multiphase transport of air containing water droplets. In our experiments the dry air available in the sterile room (30% R.H.) was humidified before entering the tube, by saturation with

demineralized water. Such procedure ensured the evaporation of the droplets before impacting the mask specimen. The temperature and the R.H. in the cylinder were measured by a digital thermo-hygrometer. See the section ***Droplet size and air humidification***.

Figure 3 : Upper part of the apparatus depicting part of the column and the aerosol injection via the nebulizer

Figure 4: Lower part of the apparatus with the mask sample cell and the impactor below (left). The 6 stages of the impactor highlighting the decreasing size of the pores and the sealing o-rings (right)

Figure 5: The colony count: on top results of a test carried out without a mask. On the bottom, the results of a test performed with a masks having a bacterial filtration efficiency higher than 98%. One can see the higher number of colonies in the top row and the small number of colonies in the bottom row

Droplet size and air humidification

The aerosol generation is obtained by a commercial nebulizer, and in order to ensure the normative requirements are met, in terms of mass of liquid nebulized and droplets dimension (MPS), the following procedure was followed to found the correct operative pressure:

Measure of the amount of aerosol generated: the nebulizer, filled with the operative fluid, was turned on, kept at a fixed pressure for 30 minutes and the amount of aerosol generated (liquid fraction) is weighted on an analytical balance every 10 minutes; the amount of aerosol produced in each interval was calculated by dividing the weight difference between the beginning and the end of the interval and for the density of the water (considered equal to that of the operative fluid) and for interval time. The amount of liquid atomized was the arithmetic mean of the value of the three intervals.

Measure of the Droplet Size Distribution (DSD): at the outlet section of the nebulizer, a laser diffraction system Spraytec (Malvern Panalytical, UK) was used to inspect the size of the generated liquid droplets generated by the nebulizer. The measurements were performed 20 mm downstream the outlet pipe of the nebulizer, to minimize the effects of the evaporation rate. More in detail, the DSD analysis can be carried out and reported in different ways, and the numerical frequency curve of the different particles size may be reported on a numerical or volume basis. The relative numerical frequency, $f_{i,n}$, in each size class is evaluated as:

$$f_{i,n} = \frac{n_i}{n_{tot}} 100 \quad (1)$$

where n_i is the number of the droplets in the i -class and n_{tot} the total number of the droplets.

However, in order to account for the larger volume and weight of larger droplets with respect to the smaller ones, and consequently a larger number of bacteria contained, the volumetric frequency, $f_{i,v}$, is also evaluated as:

$$f_{i,v} = \frac{n_i d_i^3}{\sum_{i=1}^j n_i d_i^3} 100 \quad (2)$$

where j is the number of analyzed classes and d_i the mean diameter of the droplets in the i -class.

The DSD obtained and effective diameter associated to the aerosol generated can be characterized by lumped parameters, and it is thus useful to define, in an objective way, the mean diameter as:

$$d_{lm} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^j n_i d_i^l}{\sum_{i=1}^j n_i d_i^m} \quad (3)$$

According to the values of l and m , it is possible to compute the numerical diameter (d_{10}), the surface-volume mean diameter (d_{32}), usually called Sauter diameter, and the volume-weighted mean diameter (d_{43}), usually called De Brouckere diameter. It should be also important to define a lumped parameter giving a quantitative information on the uniformity of the DSD to avoid that different laboratories working with same mean diameter could obtain different results because of the different DSD.

A parameter that could be simply evaluated from the experimental data of DSD, is the Span factor defined as:

$$S = \frac{d_{0.9} - d_{0.1}}{d_{0.5}} \quad (4)$$

where $d_{0.9}$ is the diameter below which 90% of the total volume of the droplet distribution is contained, in the same way is defined $d_{0.1}$ that refers to 10% of the total volume and $d_{0.5}$ that refers to 50% of the total volume.

SPLASH TEST

The blood resistance test rig was assembled as indicated by the standard norm. The whole apparatus is shown in the Figure.

Figure 3: Splash test apparatus

In brief, the apparatus is equipped by a specimen-holding frame able to accommodate the whole surgical mask prototype and of a fluid dosing system in which a **pneumatic controlled valve** is able to dispense a specified volume of blood in a jet stream (Fisnar JB1113N, NJ, United States), using the air activated syringe that is equipped by a cylindrical needle 12.7 mm long and with a 0.83 mm diameter, as requested by the standard norm.

More in detail, the whole frame was fabricated according to the specifications and the quotes indicated in the standard norm, while the mask- holder was produced by 3D-printing.

Compressed air is used by the instrument to regulate the pressure (double checked by an additional external manometer), while the valve opening time, controlled by the dosing system, allows to control the volume of synthetic blood directed towards the mask surfaces.

- The **synthetic blood** was prepared according to the following method: 5% w/v of Poly(ethylene glycol)-b-poly(propylene glycol)-b-poly(ethylene glycol) (Pluronic® F-108, Sigma Aldrich, Italy) was added to 1 L of distilled water previously boiled for at least 5 min. The solution was kept under agitation for 1 h and subsequently sonicated for 15 min. 30 g of Rhodamine (purity > 95%, Sigma Life Science USA) was added to the solution with a further agitation for 40-60 min, using an orbital shaker.
- The **surface tension** of the synthetic blood was measured three times by the **pendant drop method** using a Theta Lite tensiometer (Biolin Scientific, Sweden). The solution has a surface tension equal to **41.45 mN/m**.
- **Density** was measured in triplicate using a 1.0 mL Hamilton syringe and an AX224 Sartorius balance (Lab Instruments GmbH & Co. KG Goettingen Germany) with 0.0001 g precision. The solution has a density of **1015 kg/m³**.
- Before each test the sample iwa **preconditioned** in a chamber with a relative humidity of $(85 \pm 5) \%$ at room temperature $(21 \pm 5) ^\circ\text{C}$ and the pressure of the air and the volume of the blood sprayed wwere checked.
- In a typical analysis, the sample was mounted on the mask-holder and sprayed by **2 mL of synthetic blood jet at a pressure of 16.0 kPa** considering a distance from the needle to the mask of (300 ± 10) mm and the center of the specimen as the target area. For each mask prototype, the same test was repeated at least five times considering five different samples.
- After testing, medial face mask pass/fail determinations were based on simple **visual detection** of synthetic blood. However, mask samples with particular color, written or design need the addition of talcum powder to rule out the possibility of blood trail.

- The standard norm imposes an acceptable quality limit (AQL) of 4%, which is defined on a number of samples of 32. Since during the pandemic the number of masks supplied for each type was not enough for the analysis, the 4% was considered on a smaller number of sample but each sample tested had to pass the test to be classified as a IIR mask.

BIOBURDEN

The test aims to evaluate quantitatively the number of microorganisms present on the mask before wearing it for the first time. Although it is crucial for the final evaluation of a surgical mask to be made available in the masked and used by the population, it may be considered of a minor relevance with respect to the previous tests when a mask prototype is first evaluated to determine its performances. To some extent, bioburden tests evaluate the cleanliness of the production line and of the effectiveness of the sterilization and packaging lines after the production

Project results

1) The website

The project resulted in the publication of a new website hosted permanently by UNIBO at the address https://site.unibo.it/open_mask_lab and uploaded on Zenodo at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4778519>. The website (see Figure 3) contains multimedia materials, pictures, and explanatory text for the tests on surgical masks. The website also contains statistics and data collected during one year of surgical mask testing at the University of Bologna. In particular

-**Homepage:** contains 3 explanatory videos with subtitles about the main tests for surgical masks: BFE, Breathability test, Splash resistance test according to EN 14683.

-**Tests:** contains detailed information about the methodology of the various tests and in particular

- a) https://site.unibo.it/open_mask_lab/en/tests/breathability-test
- b) https://site.unibo.it/open_mask_lab/en/tests/bacterial-filtration-efficiency-test
- c) https://site.unibo.it/open_mask_lab/en/tests/splash-test

-**Agenda:** a section with all the events related to mask testing

-**Useful links page:** contains a list of links on surgical masks and facial masks (PPE).

Figure 4: The Website homepage

2) The video tutorials

We produced 3 explanatory videos with subtitles about the main tests for surgical masks
BFE test EN 14683 (Youtube <https://youtu.be/skaSetCxzck> and on Zenodo platform <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4738941>)

Breathability test EN 14683 (Youtube <https://youtu.be/kWLyxw36Zhs> and Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4739082>)

Splash resistance test EN 14683 (Youtube <https://youtu.be/vwhE9P6RMSQ> and Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4740608>)

3) The open access publications

1 open access paper is under preparation entitled

“One year of surgical mask testing at the University of Bologna labs: lessons learned from data analysis and correlation” under submission (OPEN ACCESS)

4) Data and correlations

Tests

The project produced a large number of data, which can be combined to obtain correlations and will be contained in the open access publications. The Laboratory started its activity on March 24th 2020. As of Dec 31st 2020, 602 prototypes were tested, with nearly 1200 tests performed overall.

Certifiability of tested masks

The first months of testing were characterized by a higher number of tests and a lower number of masks that could be successfully certified, as reported in Figure 4. Over time and with increasing knowledge of the main requirements for being certifiable, the number of masks successfully passing all the tests increased, leading to a higher number of new masks potentially ready to enter the market during November and December 2020.

Figure 5: Time evolution of masks certifiability-Year 2020. Left: total number of masks which were tested, fraction of certified and non certified masks. Right: percentage of certified masks over total masks tested as a function of time.

Road to certification

In order to obtain the certification according to EN 14683:2019, a specific testing order must be followed. In particular, the breathability test represents the first step of the road to certification. Being quite simple and fast to perform, this test sets the schedule for other tests and allows to exclude rapidly non-certifiable masks. Considering a 10 months period, a failing rate for breathability is of 36 masks out of 100, reaching a peak of 47/100 during the first period of emergency. Referring to masks that successfully passed the breathability test, around 60% presented ΔP lower than 40 Pa/cm² and, in most of the cases, were subjected to the second test on the road, namely the BFE. The remaining 40% of masks with ΔP between 40 and 60 Pa/cm², when explicitly required by the client, was subjected to BFE test as a potential IIR type masks.

Analysis of BFE tests performed on potential I and II type masks showed that only a small part, namely 20 out of 100 masks, presented BFE higher than 95%, out of which 15 masks performed at BFE higher than 98%. In the case of masks with ΔP between 40 and 60 Pa/cm², just 27% could be potentially classified as IIR type mask, showing a BFE higher or equal to 98%.

In order to be classified as IIR type, after showing satisfying results in breathability and BFE tests, the mask has to be subjected to splash test with synthetic blood. If not passed, unfortunately the mask can't be certified.

The final test to assess the certifiability verifies the microbial cleanliness of the masks (Bioburden). The norm requires a value < 30 CFU/g of mask in order to verify the sterility of production line and thus in order to allow the use of mask as a protection device. Bioburden does not evaluate directly the mask performance, but instead it evaluates the sterilization process used during the production. For this reason, the negative result does not potentially affect the possibility of mask certification, once a more efficient sterilization process is implemented for its production.

Finally, considering a total of 448 masks for which all tests were performed, just 9% arrived till a finish line on the road to certification. Most part of the passed masks, namely 47%, were classified as type II, while just 20% could be classified as type I surgical mask. In figure 5 we report a representation of the road with indication of failure stage for different masks.

Figure 6 Road to certification and point of failure of tested masks.

Correlations between mask properties

It is possible to correlate the pressure drop ΔP to the bacterial filtration efficiency, two quantities that represent respectively the barrier to air molecules and to bacteria filtration. It can be seen (Figure 6) that increasing ΔP , the physical barrier to bacterial filtration also increases. However, the Bacterial filtration ability of the mask is mainly guaranteed by the electrostatic forces rather than by the physical barrier. Therefore this type of correlation does not carry a predictive character.

Figure 7 Correlation between Bacterial filtration efficiency (barrier to bacteria) and Pressure Drop ΔP (Barrier to air) for the various masks tested. The brown line indicates the average trend of the correlation. Different colors indicate masks with different ranges of breathability.

Project results dissemination

The website, videos and papers were advertised during many occasions and on social media such as LinkedIn, Facebook and the UNIBO magazine.

On May 5th 2021 a webinar was given by Cristiana Boi on the European Membrane Society Youtube Live streaming platform <https://youtu.be/e8-HuOrrWy4>

Justification of expenses

Expenses regarded the purchase of

a) CONTROL INSTRUMENTATION

- a notebook and a hard drive for lab data acquisition about BFE and breathability. (1492.74 €)
- a pressure sensor for the BFE test (646.6 €)
- manometers required for the breathability test (7604.26 €)

for a total of **9743.6** euros (originally planned 14000 €. Unfortunately due to the short duration of the project and time restrictions we could not attribute some of the originally planned purchases, such as flowmeters, to this project as we were not able to place the order and receive the equipment in due time).

b) EQUIPMENT and MACHINERY required for tests

- an analytical balance to weigh the samples (760.75 €)
- a thermostatic bath (732 €) and a cooled incubator (4626.24 €) to condition mask samples prior to breathability, BFE and splash tests
- a vacuum pump required for the BFE test (3867.64 €)
- an ultrafiltration cell for testing both pressure drop (breathability) and the filtration efficiency on small scale specimens, and for the evaluation of the penetration of liquid species, e.g. synthetic blood (splash test) or contaminated water (2278.96 €)
- a thermobalance used to evaluate the moisture content in the mask prototype, once conditioned at a certain humidity (research purpose) (1262.7 €)
- an ultrasonic bath to clean the glassware used in sample preparation, conditioning and for testing (1666.08 €)
- a vial agitator used for the preparation of the bacterial suspension (256.10 €)
- a vacuum oven used to condition the mask prototypes, using the oven as climatic chamber (4660.4 €)
- a magnetic stirrer for preparing the solutions (174.46 €)

for a total of **20279.33** € (originally planned 14000 €: additional costs came mostly from the fact that a new vacuum oven was purchased instead of the one already existing in the lab, reserved to evacuate masks prior to testing in order to avoid contamination of the materials with other samples used in the lab).

c) CONSUMABLES

- fittings, pipes and adapters required to carry out the breathability and BFE test (9186.91€)
- glassware such as flasks, beakers, filters, needed to prepare bacterial solutions required for the bacterial filtration efficiency test and for the splash resistance test (1738.7 €+1333.64 €)

for a total of **12259.25** € (originally planned 6000 €: additional costs came from the fact that vacuum-proof or pressure-proof fittings were purchased instead of standard ones, for extra safety of the tests in order to avoid contamination of the materials or of the external environment during testing).

d) SOFTWARE : no expenses were made on software as the standard software package available at UniBo was used. (2000 € originally planned)

e) WEBSITE preparation, domain acquisition: no expenses were made on website as the tools and platforms available at UniBo were used, as well as the available domain space. (3000 € originally planned)

f) TRAVEL: no travel was performed due to COVID-related restrictions (2000 € originally planned)

g) OPEN ACCESS publications: the open access publications are undergoing and they will be paid with other funds after the end of the project, due to time restrictions it was not possible to attribute such expenses to the project (1000 € originally planned)

h) TECHNICIAN: no specialized technician work was used as the assembling was performed by internal University staff. (2000 € originally planned)

In the end we purchased Instrumentation, Equipment and consumables for a total of **42282.18 €**, which is less than the originally planned budget of 45000 €.

Unfortunately due to the short duration of the project and time restrictions, as well as the procurement guidelines on the purchase of equipment, we could not attribute some of the originally planned purchases to this project as we were not able to place the order and receive the equipment in due time. The other variations to the budget are explained in the detail in the list above and in the pictures below (Figures 7 and 8 respectively).

DETAILED SPECIFICATION OF COSTS space to be filled out by applicant					
N°	Cost item	Quantity	Price	Sum	Description
01	Control instrumentation: Manometers, flowmeters, etc	1	€ 14 000.00	€ 14 000.00	Control instrumentation: Manometers, flowmeters, etc for setting up new equipment for mask tests for DEMO purposes
02	Machinery: pumps and similar, valves, columns, impactor	1	€ 14 000.00	€ 14 000.00	Machinery: pumps and similar, valves, columns, impactor for setting up new equipment for mask tests for DEMO purposes
03	Consumables (gases, bacteria, solvents, tubing, fittings)	1	€ 6 000.00	€ 6 000.00	Consumables required to carry out the tests for DEMO purposes
04	Software for data analysis and for video tutorials preparation, etc.:	1	€ 2 000.00	€ 2 000.00	Software for data analysis to produce correlations to be shared in the platform and for video tutorials preparation, etc.:
05	Website preparation and domain acquisition	1	€ 3 000.00	€ 3 000.00	Website preparation and domain acquisition: money to pay the domain and the website configuration, tools for the statistics of the accesses
06	Travel	1	€ 2 000.00	€ 2 000.00	Travels required for training in presence or for dissemination to conferences or for meeting possible partners
07	Open access publications	2	€ 1 000.00	€ 2 000.00	Costs estimated for 2 publications "Open access" in Journals
08	Technician (welding, tubing assembling etc.)	1	€ 2 000.00	€ 2 000.00	Costs of technician work required to assemble the new testing equipment for DEMO purposes

Figure 8: Originally planned budget

DETAILED SPECIFICATION OF COSTS space to be filled out by applicant					
N°	Cost item	Quantity	Price	Sum	Description
01	Control instrumentation: Manometers, flowmeters, etc	1	€ 9 743.60	€ 9 743.60	Control instrumentation: Manometers, notebook for data acquisition in the lab
02	Machinery: pumps and similar, valves, columns, impactor	1	€ 20 279.33	€ 20 279.33	Machinery: pump, balance, oven, thermostatic bath and chamber, ultrasonic bath, agitator, stirrer
03	Consumables (gases, bacteria, solvents, tubing, fittings)	1	€ 12 259.25	€ 12 259.25	Consumables like glassware to prepare the tests and fittings
04	Software for data analysis and for video tutorials preparation, etc.:	1	€ -	€ -	No new software was purchased. The standard software available at UniBo was used
05	Website preparation and domain acquisition	1	€ -	€ -	The website was prepared by staff at UniBo and on a site owned by UniBo
06	Travel	1	€ -	€ -	No travel was possible due to the pandemics restrictions
07	Open access publications	1	€ -	€ -	The publications are under preparation right now and the costs for their open access publications will be allocated on other fund
08	Technician (welding, tubing assembling etc.)	1	€ -	€ -	The technician work was not required during the duration of the project. Necessary work was carried out by UniBo personnel
09				€ -	
				Requested value:	€ 42 282.18

Figure 9: Actual budget

Bologna
August 26th 2021

Maria Grazia De Angelis

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Matteo Minelli

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